

NOTICE

The PDFs of journal articles and other documents that IRRI Library provides, may be protected by Copyright Law, in which case no reproduction or redistribution is permitted. To copy, to republish, to post on servers, or to redistribute to lists, requires prior specific permission from the publisher or copyright holder. This document is provided strictly for your personal, non-commercial research and educational use.

Moncompu Rice Research Station. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with two replications. Seedlings were planted at 20 × 15-cm spacing and the plot fertilized with 70-35-35 kg NPK/ha in three splits.

Cultivars were affected by GSV at maximum tillering. Incidence was heavy, in some plots all plants died.

Susceptibility of promising rice cultivars to GSV. Moncompu, India, 1988 wet season.

Cross	Disease score (0-9)	
IET10512	IET2815/Khonorollo	3
IET10513	RP79-9/Salumpikit	2
IET11057	Rasi/IET7332	3
IET11058	Rajendra/IR30	8
IET11060	Mashuri/Jaya	3
IET11062	B 29826/SR 62-31-4	2
IET11063	IR30/Babawa// IR2071-625-1-25-2	5
IET11064	TKM6/IET1444	8
IET11066	Phalguna/TKM6	5
IET11067	Sabarmati/Sona	8
IET11068	CR44-35/W12708	5
IET11069	IR8/IET4141	5
IET11070	Pusa 2-21/WGL 28171	8
IET11071	Jaya/IET4146	9
IET11072	IET4107/WGL22245	9
IET11073	IR8/Surekha	9
IET11074	IR8/Surekha	8
IET11075	IR8/Surekha	8
IET11076	IR8/Surekha	8
IET11077	Rasi/Gampai	8
IET9381	IR1561/Ptb 33	9
IET11579	Co 13/IR26	5
IET11580	ADT32/ADT29	7
IET11581	Rajendra/IR30	7
IET11582	IR36/MTU4569	4
IET11583	BAM3/TN1	7
IET11584	OR5461/RNR32341	3
IET11585	WGL 27120/MTU// W17620/Surekha	9
IET11586	Ratna/ARC5981	3
IET11587	Sona/K118	9
IET11588	Mutant of Luchai - 12	4
IET11101	A23/TR17	4
IET11589	IET4699/RP193-1	9
IET11590	IET4699/RP193-1	4
IET11591	IET4699/RP193-1	4
IET11592	Jaya/Gampai	8
IET11593	IET7302/IET7575	9
IET11594	Sona/ARC14529	9
IET11595	Ratna/Ptb 33	9
IET11596	Rasi/Gampai	9
IET11597	IET2815/Latisail	8
IET11598	Sona/ARC5981	9
IET11599	IET7302/IET7575	9
IET11600	Ratna/ARC5981	5
IET11601	Swarnadhan/Benong	7
IET11602	Swarnadhan/Tamiang	4
IET11603	Swarnadhan/Salamat	4
-	Jaya (check)	8
-	Local (check)	4

None of the 49 cultivars in the test showed resistance to GSV (see table). Seven showed moderate resistance, 14

were moderately susceptible, 4 were susceptible, and 24 were highly susceptible. □

Virulence of six isolates of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* on rice

Y. Suryadi and T. Tjubarjat, Sukamandi
Research Institute for Food Crops, Subang,
West Java, Indonesia

We studied the virulence of six isolates of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae*, the causal organism of rice bacterial blight (BB), on four improved rice cultivars in the greenhouse 1987 and 1988 wet seasons.

Cultivars were inoculated 45 d after

transplanting by pricking the uppermost fully extended leaves with a bacterial suspension of each isolate adjusted to 10⁹ CFU/ml. Length of lesion on inoculated leaves was measured 21 d after inoculation.

Lesion length indicated that isolates differed significantly in pathogenicity and cultivars showed different susceptibilities (see table). Isolate Si 8524, representing Indonesian group IV, was the most virulent. IR64 and Dodokan (released in 1987) showed good resistance against BB isolates. □

BB lesion length on 4 rice cultivars at 21 d after inoculation. Sukamandi, 1987 and 1988 wet seasons.

Isolate	Lesion length ^a (cm)				
	IR64	IR48	Dodokan	TN1	Mean ^b
	1987				
Si8505	36.67	47.23	45.62	55.47	46.49 ab
Si8524	49.57	49.32	50.23	66.23	53.84 a
Si8401	35.80	23.47	33.67	54.17	36.78 b
Si8501	34.03	55.77	43.57	48.27	45.41 ab
Si8603	41.00	45.87	24.07	55.55	41.62 b
Si8506	33.63	35.87	31.13	40.07	35.17 b
Mean	38.45 b	42.92 b	38.21 b	53.29 a	
	1988				
Si8505	37.80	45.07	45.96	50.41	45.31 b
Si8524	50.53	58.60	52.53	61.3	55.74 a
Si8401	23.37	36.29	20.96	47.59	32.05 c
Si8501	44.73	29.39	29.17	58.77	40.51 bc
Si8603	43.23	50.53	40.15	56.83	47.68 ab
Si8506	38.03	48.90	29.50	51.27	41.92 b
Mean ^b	39.61 bc	45.13 b	36.38 c	54.36 a	

^aAv of 10 leaves inoculated. ^bOverall means for isolates and cultivars followed by the same letter do not differ significantly by DMRT (P=0.05).

Field resistance to false smut (FS) and narrow brown leaf spot (NBLS) in eastern Uttar Pradesh

R. N. Singh and A. T. Khan, N.D.
University of Agriculture and Technology,
P.O. Dabha Semar, District Faizabad
224133, Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

FS caused by *Ustilaginoidea virens* (Cke.) Takahashi and NBLS caused by

Cercospora oryzae Miyake are important diseases in eastern UP. We tested 231 rice genotypes for resistance during 1986-87 and 1987-88 hot wet seasons (1 Jun-30 Nov). Natural disease pressure was high in both years. All trial plots were irrigated and fertilized with 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha. Disease was rated by the Standard evaluation system for rice, at the dough stage for NBLS and at the hard dough to maturity stage for FS.

NOTICE

The PDFs of journal articles and other documents that IRRI Library provides, may be protected by Copyright Law, in which case no reproduction or redistribution is permitted. To copy, to republish, to post on servers, or to redistribute to lists, requires prior specific permission from the publisher or copyright holder. This document is provided strictly for your personal, non-commercial research and educational use.

Resistance to 2 diseases in Faizabad, UP, India.

Disease	Entries ^a (%)			
	Resistant ^b	Moderately susceptible	Susceptible	Probable escapes
False smut	42.99	23.98	6.79	26.24
Narrow brown leaf spot	65.67	3.43	13.74	17.16

^aBased on 221 genotypes tested against FS, 231 tested against NBLs. ^bReaction: 0 = probable escape, 1-3 = resistant, 4-6 = moderately susceptible, 7-9 = susceptible.

Entries maturing in Sep generally escaped FS and those in Oct, NBLs: 37 genotypes escaped both diseases and 71 showed resistance to both (see table). FS pressure starts building in Oct and is highest in varieties that mature in Nov. NBLs pressure starts building in Nov and is highest in varieties that mature in late Nov and Dec. □

Sources of resistance to rice yellow dwarf and its vector

G. N. Rao and P. Narayanasamy, Plant Pathology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We tested 24 rice genotypes for resistance to rice yellow dwarf (RYD) and its green leafhopper (GLH) vector (*Nephotettix virescens* Distant).

First- and second-instar GLH nymphs were allowed 48 h acquisition feeding on

RYD source plants and confined on healthy rice plants for 30 d to complete the latent period. Twenty 7-d-old test seedlings of each genotype were placed individually in test tubes, and inoculated with 2 GLH/tube for 24 h. Inoculated seedlings were planted in earthen pots and disease symptoms monitored.

The genotypes also were tested for reaction to GLH (TN1 and PTB33 were susceptible and resistant checks) using 15 seedlings/variety in seedbox screening (4-5 second- and third-instar nymphs/seedling).

Resistance (infection range 5-30%) showed in 18 genotypes: IR64, IET7492, and IR62 recorded very low infection (see table). Incubation period was longest in IR64, followed by IR62 and IET7492. Twenty genotypes were moderately resistant or resistant to vector GLH.

IR62, IR64, and IET7492, with resistance to both RYD and GLH and with long incubation periods, are good donors for developing RYD-resistant cultivars. □

Sources of resistance to RYD and GLH.

Genotype	RYD infection (%)	Reaction ^a	Mean incubation period (d)	Increase over (%) susceptible check	GLH	
					Grade	Reaction ^b
IR64	5.0	R	40.0	43.4	3	R
IET7492	5.0	R	39.0	39.8	3	R
IR62	10.0	R	39.5	41.6	3	R
TNAU 80030	15.0	R	35.0	25.4	3	R
Tadukan	15.0	R	34.7	23.4	3	R
TNAU 831520	15.0	R	34.0	21.9	3	R
IR58	15.0	R	33.7	20.8	3	R
IR30	15.0	R	33.3	19.4	3	R
IR8	15.0	R	33.3	19.4	5	MR
RP1931-54	20.0	R	33.5	20.1	3	R
IR26	20.0	R	33.0	18.3	5	MR
IR5	20.0	R	32.5	16.5	5	MR
TNAU 831521	20.0	R	32.0	14.7	5	MR
NLR 139-69	25.0	R	33.0	18.3	5	MR
IR24	25.0	R	32.4	16.1	3	R
TNAU 80058	25.0	R	31.6	13.3	3	R
ADT 31	30.0	R	31.5	12.9	5	MR
TKM 9	30.0	R	31.5	12.9	5	MR
AD 85002	35.0	I	31.3	12.2	5	MR
TNAU 80042	40.0	I	30.5	9.3	5	MR
CO 43	40.0	I	30.5	9.3	7	S
Ponni	45.0	I	30.5	9.3	7	S
White Ponni	50.0	I	30.0	7.5	7	S
IR20	70.0	S	28.9	3.6	7	S
TN1 (susceptible check)	85.0	S	27.9	—	9	HS
PTB33 (resistant check)	—	—	—	—	1	HR
LSD (P=0.05)	—	—	0.6	—	—	—

^aR = 0.30, I = 31-60%, S = 60% infection. ^bHR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

Technique to preserve conidia of rice blast (BI) fungus

Sun Guochang and Sun Shuyuan, Plant Protection Institute, Zhejiang Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Hangzhou; and Shen Zongtan, Agronomy Department, Zhejiang Agricultural University, Hangzhou, China

We studied the effect of preservation conditions on viability and pathogenicity of conidia of four rice BI fungus *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. races.

Freshly produced conidia were washed from barley grains with distilled water. The spore suspension was passed through a general filter paper (ϕ 12 cm) in a funnel, dried at 30-35 °C, and stored in an aluminum box (ϕ 10 × H15 cm) at ambient temperature (-4-35 °C) and in a desiccator at three temperatures: ambient, 4 °C, and -20 °C.

Conidia viability was evaluated every 3-4 mo in a drop of distilled water on a concave slide incubated at 28 °C for 24 h. Pathogenicity was tested by